

The Doula movement: Bridging the gap in End-of -life care

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The term “doula” is a Greek word (doule), meaning a woman’s servant, and is historically applied to birth or postpartum doulas. They provide companionship, continuous labour support, and postpartum care, as well as emotional, physical, and non-medical assistance during labour, and facilitate communication between the mother/family and her medical staff. (Petrie and Larimore, W. L.,2008, Gilliland, A. L., 2002) The success of birth doulas has inspired the development of specialized doulas in end- of -life care, called death doulas. It is also known as an end-of-life doula, soul midwife, death coach, dying guide, death midwife, and palliative care doula. The role of death fistulas remains relatively new. They provide support to terminally ill patients and their families during the final month or week of life, death, and after death. (Rawlings, D.,2020, Borgstrom, E.,2024)

Death doulas are available worldwide, including in Brazil, Canada, the Czech Republic, Germany, Ireland, Italy, Japan, New Zealand, Russia, the UK, and the US. In fact, fatally affected individuals work to improve life and death. This involves helping patients with funeral plans, talking to people through death processes, making care appointments, and planning living estates. Some death doulas may even offer a company or companionship to the patient on certain occasions. (Borgstrom, E.,2024) A doula who assists a person nearing the end of their life plays crucial roles in various areas: they establish the dying person's wishes, facilitate open dialogues to reduce fear and loneliness, facilitate the creation of advance plans for the end of life, guide individuals through health and social care services, support crucial decisions, demonstrate practicality, act as a point of contact for other services, and provide home support. They also collaborate with other healthcare professionals in hospitals, hospices, care homes, and nursing homes to coordinate assistance and provide respite, spend time with dying individuals, assist with funeral formalities, and provide ongoing emotional support for the bereaved. (End of Life Doula UK, 2024)

End-of-life care is a significant component of the healthcare system, although classical medical paradigms are only a small part of a dying person's experience. Studies

worldwide have proven that, on average, most patients spend the final stages of their lives in various environments. Less than 10% of patients received professional care. (GOV.UK *Patterns of care, England, 2021*, GOV.UK *Statistical commentary, 2023*) In fact, the traditional model of healthcare specifically offers end-of-life care services; this is only a minor part of the dying individual's time. This calls for a broader public health approach that also creates an enabling environment beyond clinical care with aspects such as community engagement and social support systems. In the last two decades, compassionate communities have made enormous strides: local civic initiatives in which neighbours, schools, workplaces, and a myriad of other community organisations come together to provide social support to people with life-limiting illnesses, the frail elderly, and those in long-term caregiving tasks or experiencing grief. Compassionate cities include the giants of the business world, trade unions, religious institutions, social media, cultural centres, and sports associations, as well as the rest of the world, which has started seeing end-of-life care as a civic duty. These cities create policies and programmes that meet the needs of their citizens, with a strong support network for their members. (Abel and Kellehear 2022)

The doula movement, which aims to support individuals during their final stages of life, is at the heart of this public health initiative, focusing on supporting people during most of their time spent outside of professional care. Trained nonprofessional's, known as doulas, provide individuals at the end of life with emotional, social, and practical support. Formalisation and public presence are essential for the doula movement to become more mainstream and politically recognised. Doulas play a dual role in public health, not only accompanying dying, but also addressing the social and psychological consequences of death, such as loneliness, anxiety, depression, stigma, and social rejection. Engaging in harm reduction and early intervention helps mitigate these negative effects and promotes positive aspects of end-of-life care, such as emotional well-being and social support, enhancing the overall quality of life for dying individuals and their families. Integrating doulas into the mainstream end-of-life care system necessitates boosting public health education and raising the public image. Given that the doula approach is still relatively new and is currently under investigation and study, further research is necessary to examine doula strategy and system identification.

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